

On the Decidability of Distributed Tasks with Output Sets under Asynchrony and Any Number of Crashes

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Abstract

In this paper, we define a new class of distributed tasks, called *SOS tasks* (for *Set of Output Sets tasks*), defined by the set O of distinct output sets of values that can be produced. We then demonstrate that this class of tasks is decidable: there exists an effective procedure that determines whether any SOS task is solvable asynchronously under t crashes. The decision rule is as follows. Every SOS task is solvable when $t = 0$. For $t > 0$, an SOS task is solvable if and only if its *SOS graph* $G = (O, \subset)$ is connected. In this graph, each vertex is an output set in O , and two vertices are linked by an edge whenever one output set includes the other. One of the surprising implications of our results is that, without a validity property, k -set agreement is solvable under any number of crashes $t \geq 0$ for $k > 1$, and unsolvable under $t > 0$ crashes only for $k = 1$ (consensus). Finally, we study a novel family of tasks called d -disagreement, which requires the system to always produce d different output values, and we show that its implementability condition is related to the harmonic series.

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1 Introduction

Many problems studied in distributed computing can be represented as *tasks*, i.e., abstractions where every participant has at most one input value and at most one output value. Consensus, for example, is a task where each participant proposes a value (the inputs), and all participants must decide on the same value (the outputs) from among the initial proposals. Although tasks cannot capture some distributed problems (in particular, long-lived primitives such as shared registers or transactional objects), they remain a particularly useful abstraction for studying the solvability boundaries of distributed computing.

Towards a theory of distributed decidability One of the grand challenges of distributed computing involves determining which families of distributed problems are decidable and which ones are not. Decidability in this context means that there exists an effective procedure determining if a given distributed problem is solvable in a given computing model or not. It has been shown that distributed computing as a whole is undecidable, as undecidable families of tasks have been identified within it, in particular, the class of asynchronous tasks under at least 2 crashes [10, 13]. But undecidability in the general case does not prevent some classes of tasks to still be decidable: indeed, all asynchronous tasks under at most 1 crash [3, 4, 18], or in the presence of only initial crashes [22], are decidable. The present work is part of this endeavour: it focuses on a particular class of tasks that we call *SOS tasks*, and it shows that there exists a procedure determining whether any of these SOS tasks can be implemented asynchronously under any number of crashes. Eventually, by progressively identifying new classes of decidable and undecidable tasks, it will be possible to build an exhaustive theory of distributed decidability that is as fundamental to this field as computability theory is to sequential computing.

The limitations of traditional approaches Traditionally, a distributed task is defined as one specific triplet (I, O, \rightarrow) , where I and O are respectively the input and output domains of the task, and \rightarrow is a mapping between the inputs and outputs. In this context, combinatorial topology is one of the most powerful approaches for studying the solvability and decidability of tasks [12]. With combinatorial topology, the input and output domains I, O are modelled as *simplicial complexes*, and the mapping \rightarrow is a *carrier map* (representing the task specification) between the input simplexes and output simplexes. However, this traditional approach has some limitations.

- *Rigidity of the classical task definition.* In distributed computing, problem definitions are often not limited to a single triplet (I, O, \rightarrow) , as they can allow multiple implementations that each have different possible triplets (I, O, \rightarrow) . For instance, median consensus (which must decide the median value from those proposed) and majority consensus (which must decide the most frequent value from those proposed) are represented as two different triplets (I, O, \rightarrow) as they do not entail the same mapping between the inputs and outputs, however they are both valid solutions to the consensus problem [9].
- *Restricted expressiveness of simplicial complexes.* An important requirement of simplicial complexes is that they must be “closed under inclusion”, which means that, for each simplex in a complex, all its subsimplexes must also be in the complex. In practice, this means that many important distributed problems cannot be effectively captured by simplicial complexes. For instance, the output of tasks like strong symmetry breaking (SSB) [16], renaming [7], or election [21, 16] cannot be captured as classical simplicial complexes, as they have executions where the processes of the system output multiple distinct values (e.g., 0 and 1), but they do not have executions producing each of these values individually (resp., executions for 0 and executions for 1). To address this limitation, some approaches rely on colored simplicial complexes, but doing so introduces significant additional complexity.

Our approach: focusing on the output sets of tasks In this paper, we address the previous limitations of traditional approaches by developing a novel way of defining and studying tasks. More precisely, we depart from the classical method where a task is defined as a triplet (I, O, \rightarrow) , and develop a new framework relaxing the closedness constraint of simplicial approaches, and allowing tasks to have multiple valid instances.

Building upon this framework, we extend the *Set of Output Sets* (or *SOS*) approach introduced by Albouy *et al.* for considering tasks with binary output values [2]. To this

end, we formalize and define the class of *SOS tasks*, capturing both binary and multivalued output sets, where validity, output multiplicity, and process identities are disregarded. These SOS tasks are defined by the set of distinct output values that they can produce across their executions, called their *set of output sets*. Our approach does not capture the class of tasks that are reliant on validity or process identities for instance, but in exchange, it allows us to identify a new class of distributed decidability via the study of SOS tasks (whereas it has been shown that the classical approach is undecidable [10, 13]).

Contributions and roadmap Our contributions are the following.

- *A novel framework for studying distributed tasks.* We introduce in Section 2 a new methodology for expressing and analyzing tasks. Specifically, we present in Section 2.1 our computing model, with its abstract communication medium that can be realized asynchronously under any number of crashes from traditional models such as message-passing or shared memory. We then describe in Section 2.2 a new formalization of tasks generalizing the classical approach, enabling tasks to have multiple valid implementations, and allowing us to precisely define the solvability and decidability of tasks.
- *A new class of distributed decidability: SOS tasks.* We study in Section 3 the particular class of SOS tasks T_O , which are defined by the set of output sets O that they can produce. We then show that this class is decidable, i.e., we provide a decision rule for determining whether any SOS task T_O can be solved asynchronously under some number of crashes t . This rule can be stated as: T_O is always solvable if $t = 0$, and it is solvable with $t > 0$ if and only if the graph $G = (O, \subset)$ is weakly connected. The vertices of this graph are the output sets in O , and its edges are derived from the inclusions between these output sets.¹ Interestingly, our results have direct implications for k -set agreement. Indeed, we can define *validity-less k -set agreement* as an SOS task, and show that it can be solved under more than k crashes for $k > 1$, but only without crashes for $k = 1$ (consensus). Hence, this demonstrates a fundamental cut between consensus and >1 -set agreement. To the best of our knowledge, we are the first ones to study the decidability of a particular subclass of tasks under any crash tolerance, instead of studying the decidability of all tasks under a specific crash tolerance.
- *A particular family of SOS task: d -disagreement.* Finally, we look at a special case of SOS tasks, which we call d -disagreement, and which requires the system to always produce d different output values (hence the system “disagrees”). This problem can have multiple interesting applications, especially in the context of fault-tolerant load balancing. For example, if a distributed system has to execute d idempotent jobs J_1, \dots, J_d in parallel in the presence of up to t crashes, d -disagreement can be used, such that every process with output value $i \in [1..d]$ executes job J_i . This effectively guarantees that all jobs are eventually executed despite crashes. The d -disagreement problem was introduced in its binary version by Albouy *et al.* [2], but the present paper provides its definition in terms of SOS tasks and generalizes it to the multivalued case. We then provide an impossibility proof and an algorithm demonstrating that the implementability condition of d -disagreement is tied to the harmonic series. Indeed, under t crashes, the number of processes required to solve disagreement is approximately $H_d(t + 1)$, where H_d is the d -th harmonic number.

Section 5 exposes the research landscape in which this work is situated, and concluding

¹ Specifically, we consider the undirected version of G , which is sometimes referred to as the *comparability graph* of (O, \subset) .

remarks are provided in Section 6. For presentation clarity and completeness, we provide the full correctness proof of our first algorithm in Appendix A, and we provide new proofs for the necessity and sufficiency of non-resilient SOS tasks in Appendix B.

2 Computing Model and Problem Formalization

For clarity, we provide in Table 1 a list of concepts and notations used in this paper.

2.1 Computing Model

Process model. We consider a distributed system with a set $P = \{p, p', \dots\}$ of processes ($|P| = n$). Processes are deterministic computing entities that take steps according to their local state and the events they observe, following an algorithm A . Failures are restricted to crash faults: in an execution of the system, a process may halt prematurely and take no further steps, but it does not deviate from its algorithm before crashing. We assume an upper bound t on the number of processes that may crash in an execution, with $0 \leq t \leq n$. A process that does not crash in an execution E is said to be *correct* in E . We also assume that all processes have access to their own private local clocks, which may run at a different pace, and which allow them to set local timeouts.

Communication model Processes interact through a generic asynchronous communication medium that is *reliable*: it does not suppress, duplicate, or corrupt communicated information. Every process $p \in P$ has access to two abstract operations:

- **communicate** I : process p disseminates some information I to all the system processes;
- **observe** I (callback event): process p is notified that information I was communicated.

The medium guarantees that all correct processes eventually obtain a consistent view of the set of communicated information, while crashed processes may only have partial but always valid views. More formally, the communication abstraction satisfies the following properties (the “C” prefix stands for “communication”).

- **C-Validity:** If a process p observes information I , then I must have been previously communicated by some process p' .
- **C-Integrity:** Any process p observes some information I communicated by a given process p' at most once.
- **C-Local-Termination:** If a correct process p communicates information I , then some correct process p' (if there is any) eventually observes I .
- **C-Global-Termination:** If a correct process p observes information I , then all correct processes eventually observe I .

(Note that these properties are similar to those of reliable broadcast.) These communicate/observe operations can be implemented straightforwardly on top of classic asynchronous communication media such as message-passing networks or shared memory, regardless of

Concept or notation	Meaning
$p \in P$	Process p in the set of processes in the system P
n	Number of processes in the system ($0 \leq n = P $)
t	Upper bound on the number of crashed processes ($0 \leq t \leq n$)
T, A, E	Task, algorithm, execution
\mathbb{V}, \mathbb{U}	Universe of values, Universe of pairs of input/output vectors
\perp	Sentinel value denoting no input/output ($\perp \notin \mathbb{V}$)
$V_{\text{in}}, V_{\text{out}} \in (\mathbb{V} \cup \{\perp\})^n$	Input and output vectors of size n
\star	Unspecified value

■ **Table 1** Concepts and notations used in this paper.

the number of crashes t [11]. We emphasize that our model does not place any bounds on communication delays. Therefore, any ordering or timing of observations that is consistent with the above properties can occur. This assumption is standard in asynchronous models and is only used in some of our correctness proofs (namely, Theorem 4 and Theorem 28).

2.2 Problem Formalization

Input and output vectors For some $n \in \mathbb{N}$, a given instance of a distributed task takes an input vector $V_{\text{in}} = (v_{\text{in}}^1, \dots, v_{\text{in}}^n)$ and returns an output vector $V_{\text{out}} = (v_{\text{out}}^1, \dots, v_{\text{out}}^n)$, where the i -th value v_{in}^i in V_{in} (resp. v_{out}^i in V_{out}) corresponds to the input (resp. output) value of process $p_i \in P$. The values in the input and output vectors belong to the set $\mathbb{V} \cup \{\perp\}$, where \mathbb{V} is the universe of values (of finite size) and $\perp \notin \mathbb{V}$ is a sentinel value that represents no input or no output. In an execution, a process $p \in P$ can output at most one value v using the operation `output` v (multiple invocations of `output` by p must be for the same value v).

Let us define the universe of all pairs of input/output vectors as $\mathbb{U} = \bigcup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} ((\mathbb{V} \cup \{\perp\})^n) \times (\mathbb{V} \cup \{\perp\})^n$: the n -exponentiation gives the set of all possible vectors of size n and the union merges all pairs of different sizes obtained previously.

Task instances, tasks, and algorithms A task instance τ is a nonempty set of pairs $(V_{\text{in}}, V_{\text{out}})$ of input/output vectors of the same size, representing all admissible input-output mappings of that instance. A task $T = \{\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots\}$ is a set of task instances. A task T is *solvable* under asynchrony and t crashes if at least one of its instances $\tau \in T$ can be implemented by some asynchronous algorithm tolerating up to t crashes. Informally, an algorithm A *implements* a task instance τ under asynchrony and up to t crashes if the set of $(V_{\text{in}}, V_{\text{out}})$ pairs that A can produce across all its executions is exactly τ . A task instance τ *supports* a system size n if it contains at least one pair of vectors of size n ; likewise, an algorithm A *supports* a system size n if it admits executions with n processes. A class of tasks $\mathcal{T} = \{T_1, T_2, \dots\}$ is *decidable* under asynchrony and up to t crashes if there exists an effective procedure determining whether each task in \mathcal{T} is solvable.

Set of output sets (SOS) We define the *output set* of an output vector V_{out} as the set of distinct output values in V_{out} , ignoring order, multiplicity, and \perp : $OS(V_{\text{out}}) = \{v_{\text{out}}^i \in V_{\text{out}} \mid v_{\text{out}}^i \neq \perp\}$. The *set of output sets* (SOS) of a task instance τ is then $SOS(\tau) = \{OS(V_{\text{out}}) \mid (V_{\text{in}}, V_{\text{out}}) \in \tau\}$. Every SOS $O \subseteq 2^{\mathbb{V}}$ must be non-empty, but O can contain the empty set if the task instance has executions that produce no output values. As \mathbb{V} is finite, then O is also necessarily finite.

SOS tasks Given some set of output sets O , an SOS task T_O is a task that, for every defined system size n , contains all instances that (i) produce SOS O and (ii) have a full mapping between input and output vectors of the same size (meaning that inputs are not used to determine outputs, hence the task is “validity-less”). More formally, we have the following.

► **Definition 1** (SOS task). *An SOS task T_O with SOS $O \subseteq 2^{\mathbb{V}}$, $O \neq \emptyset$ is defined as follows. Let τ_n be the subset of τ containing all pairs of vectors of size n .*

$$T_O = \left\{ \tau \subseteq \mathbb{U}, \tau \neq \emptyset \mid \forall n \in \mathbb{N} : \tau_n \neq \emptyset \implies \begin{aligned} & (SOS(\tau_n) = O && \text{(constraint (i))} \\ & \wedge (\forall (V_{\text{in}}, \star), (\star, V_{\text{out}}) \in \tau_n : (V_{\text{in}}, V_{\text{out}}) \in \tau_n) \end{aligned} \right\}. && \text{(constraint (ii))}$$

For example, consider a task instance τ that must produce $O = \{\{1\}, \{1, 2\}\}$ for pairs of vectors of size $n = 2$ given $\mathbb{V} = \{1, 2\}$. Constraint (i) requires that the output sets produced

across all pairs in τ_2 are exactly O . Concretely, τ_2 must contain some output vectors in $\{(1, 1), (1, \perp), (\perp, 1)\}$ to yield output set $\{1\} \in O$, and some output vectors in $\{(1, 2), (2, 1)\}$ to yield output set $\{1, 2\} \in O$. Constraint (ii) requires that every input vector in τ_2 (e.g., $(1, 1), (1, 2), (2, \perp), \dots$) is paired with each of these output vectors (i.e., inputs do not constrain outputs). In other words, τ_2 is the full Cartesian product of all size-2 input vectors with all size-2 output vectors whose output sets lie in O .

Therefore, solving an SOS task T_O under asynchrony and t crashes reduces to providing an asynchronous algorithm A tolerating up to t crashes and satisfying constraints (i) and (ii) of Definition 1. To satisfy constraint (ii), it suffices that A ignores the input values of the processes: for a given size n , if all output vectors can be produced regardless of the input vector, then there is a total mapping between inputs and outputs. To satisfy constraint (i), A must fulfill the following two properties.

- *Safety*: Every execution of A produces an output vector V_{out} such that $OS(V_{\text{out}}) \in O$.
- *Completeness*: For every system size n supported by A and every output set $o \in O$, there is an execution of A producing an output vector V_{out} of size n such that $OS(V_{\text{out}}) = o$.

3 SOS Tasks are Decidable

In this section, we prove our main theorem (Theorem 3), stating that the entire class of SOS tasks is decidable under asynchrony and any number of crashes t . More precisely, we can determine whether any SOS task T_O is solvable or not in an asynchronous system with up to t crashes.

3.1 Preliminaries and main theorem

Our SOS task classification relies on the concept of SOS graphs, defined as follows.

► **Definition 2** (SOS graph). *Given an SOS task T_O with an SOS O , the $SOSGraph(O)$ function returns the SOS graph (O, E) of T_O , where the set of edges is $E \triangleq \{\{o, o'\} \mid o \subset o' \vee o' \subset o\}$.*

Informally, the SOS graph of an SOS task T_O links every pair of compatible output sets $o, o' \in O$, in the sense that it would not break safety if some processes “think” that the system produces o , while some other “think” that the system produces o' . Notice that the SOS graph of an SOS O is just the undirected version of the graph (O, \subset) . For notational convenience, we say that an SOS is *connected* if its SOS graph is connected, and *disconnected* otherwise. Likewise, we say that an SOS task is *connected* if its SOS is connected, or *disconnected* otherwise. We give in Figure 1 two examples of connected and disconnected SOS graphs. We can now state our main theorem.

► **Theorem 3** (Decidability of SOS tasks). *An SOS task T_O with output set O can be solved asynchronously under up to $t \in \mathbb{N}$ crashes if and only if $t = 0$ or $SOSGraph(O)$ is connected.*

■ **Figure 1** Examples of a connected SOS graph (on the left) for SOS $\{\{1\}, \{3\}, \{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, \{2, 3\}\}$ and a disconnected SOS graph (on the right) for SOS $\{\{1\}, \{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, \{2, 3\}\}$.

■ **Algorithm 1** Asynchronous algorithm implementing all connected SOS tasks T_O with SOS O assuming $n \geq |V|(t + 1)$, where $V = \bigcup O$ is the set of all output values in O .

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1 instantiation parameters: a finite walk  $SOSWalk_O$  of  $SOSGraph(O)$ .
2 initialization: pick a set of leader processes  $P_{leader} \subseteq P$  such that  $|P_{leader}| > t$ ; given  $V = \bigcup O$ 
   the set of all possible output values in  $O$ , create partition  $P_1, \dots, P_{|V|}$  of  $P$  s.t.
    $\forall i \in [1..|V|], |P_i| > t$ .
3 code of every process  $p_{leader} \in P_{leader}$  is
4   for  $i = 1$  to  $|SOSWalk_O|$  do
5     if  $i \neq |SOSWalk_O|$  then communicate  $MOVE(i + 1)$ ;
6     wait for a predefined local time;
7     if  $p_{leader}$  observed  $MOVE(i + 1)$  from less than  $|P_{leader}|$  leaders then
8       communicate  $OUTPUTSET(o_i)$ ;
9       break.
10 code of every process  $p_v \in P_v, v \in V$  is
11   upon  $p_v$  observes some  $OUTPUTSET(o)$  where  $v \in o$  do
12     output  $v$ ;
13     exit.

```

Therefore, SOS tasks can be partitioned into two subclasses: (1) the SOS tasks that can tolerate any number of crashes (their SOS graph is connected), and (2) the SOS tasks that do not tolerate any crash (their SOS graph is disconnected). The proof of the above theorem follows from Algorithm 1/Theorem 4, presented in the next section and addressing case (1) for connected SOS tasks, and from Theorem 24 and Algorithm 3/Theorem 28, presented in Appendix B and addressing case (2) for disconnected SOS tasks. (The results presented in Appendix B are quite close to those of [18], however, the translation between the two models is not straightforward, hence we provide our own proofs in the appendix for completeness.)

Notice that the SOS task T_O with SOS $O = \{\emptyset\}$ can be trivially solved under any number of crashes, simply by having all processes of the system do nothing. Therefore, for the sake of simplicity, we consider in our classification that the empty graph $G = (\emptyset, \emptyset)$ is a special case of a connected graph, but in the remainder of this section, we only consider SOS tasks T_O whose SOS O is different from $\{\emptyset\}$.

3.2 Asynchronous t -resilient algorithm for any connected SOS

In this section, we introduce Algorithm 1, a universal t -resilient algorithm that can produce any SOS task T_O with a connected SOS O under any number of crashes $t \geq 0$, provided that $n \geq (t + 1)|V|$, where $V = \bigcup O$ is the set of all output values in O . This algorithm does not guarantee tightness in the sense that the proportion t/n of crashes tolerated in the system is usually lower than what is optimal, but it shows the solvability of all connected SOS tasks under any number of crashes t .

The algorithm is instantiated (line 1) by providing as a parameter $SOSWalk_O$, a finite walk² that visits all output sets in $SOSGraph(O)$ (recall that, in graph theory, a walk is similar to a path, but the same edge or vertex can be visited multiple times in a walk). By assumption, $G = SOSGraph(O)$ is a connected graph, hence it is straightforward to construct a walk $SOSWalk_O$ that visits all vertices of G . $SOSWalk_O = (o_1, o_2, \dots)$ is encoded as a sequence of output sets that can be iterated in order.

² A finite walk $SOSWalk_O$ can always be constructed as the SOS O is finite by definition (see Section 2.2).

At the initialization of the algorithm (line 2), a set of more than t leader processes $P_{leader} \subseteq P$ is selected, ensuring that at least one leader process does not crash. We then create a partition of $|V|$ distinct exhaustive subsets of P (where V is the set of all output values in O), each of size greater than t and associated with a distinct value $v \in V$. We only assume $n \geq |V|(t+1)$, hence every leader process $p_{leader} \in P_{leader}$ is also contained in some subset P_v of the partition of P .

Each leader processes $p_{leader} \in P_{leader}$ iterates i from 1 to $|SOSWalk_O|$ (line 4). If i is smaller than $|SOSWalk_O|$, p_{leader} communicates $MOVE(i+1)$ (line 5). After waiting a predefined local time (line 6), p_{leader} checks whether it observed $MOVE(i+1)$ from all other leaders (line 7). If it is not the case, p_{leader} communicates $OUTPUTSET(o_i)$ with the i -th element in $SOSWalk_O$ (line 8) and then exits the loop (line 9). When a process $p_v \in P_v$ (where $v \in V$) observes some $OUTPUTSET(o)$ information such that v is in o , p_v outputs v (line 12) and exits (line 13).

Correctness proof This section outlines the proof of Theorem 4, stating the correctness of Algorithm 1. For the sake of presentation, we defer the full proof of this theorem to Appendix A.

► **Theorem 4** (Correctness of Algorithm 1). *Algorithm 1 implements any given connected SOS task T_O with SOS O under asynchrony and up to t crash failures, assuming $n \geq |V|(t+1)$, where $V = \bigcup O$ is the set of all possible output value in O .*

Proof sketch. We prove safety and completeness separately.

Safety. The key insight is that, in any execution, the set of output sets communicated by leader processes (denoted $LeadersOutputSets$) is either a singleton $\{o_i\}$ or a pair $\{o_i, o_{i+1}\}$ of consecutive elements in $SOSWalk_O$. This is because, once any leader communicates $OUTPUTSET(o_i)$ and exits the loop, no leader can advance past iteration $i+1$: it will not observe all $|P_{leader}|$ $MOVE(\star)$ for iteration $i+2$, and will itself communicate $OUTPUTSET(o_{i+1})$ and exit the loop. Since each process $p_v \in P_v$ outputs v only upon observing some $OUTPUTSET(o)$ with $v \in o$, the output set produced by any execution is the union $\bigcup LeadersOutputSets$. In the singleton case, this union is $o_i \in O$. In the pair case, since o_i and o_{i+1} are adjacent in $SOSWalk_O$, one must include the other by definition of the SOS graph, so their union equals the larger of the two, which is also in O .

Completeness. We show that for every output set o_i appearing in $SOSWalk_O$, there exists an execution where $LeadersOutputSets = \{o_i\}$. This is achieved by a crash-free execution with a delay pattern such that all leaders advance in lockstep through iterations $1, \dots, i-1$ (each observing all $MOVE(\star)$ before the wait expires), but at iteration i , asynchrony causes the $MOVE(\star)$ to arrive too late, so all leaders enter the condition at line 7, communicate $OUTPUTSET(o_i)$, and exit the loop. Since $|P_v| > t$ for every value $v \in V$, at least one correct process in each relevant partition outputs its value, producing exactly o_i . ◀

3.3 The case of k -set agreement

Our decidability results for SOS tasks have surprising implications, especially in the case of k -set agreement [8], a family of tasks that output at least one and at most $k \in \mathbb{N}^*$ different values among the input values. Consensus is a special case of k -set agreement where $k = 1$. It has been shown that k -set agreement under asynchrony and up to k crashes is impossible [20, 15, 6], if the validity of the task is considered (i.e., decisions are proposals). However, it is interesting to note that this validity assumption is unnecessary to prove the impossibility of 1-set agreement/consensus [9, 1]: to preclude trivial implementations, it only suffices to require that consensus “sometimes” produces different output values, without

imposing that the output values are also input values. Our work demonstrates a remarkable discontinuity in k -set agreement: its impossibility relies on validity only for $k \geq 2$, but not for $k = 1$.

In the following, we define via our formalism the family of “validity-less” k -set agreement tasks via our SOS approach. Intuitively, in validity-less k -set agreement, all nonempty output sets of size at most k can be produced, independently of the input values of the execution (i.e., the classical k -set agreement validity property does not hold). We then show that, for $k \geq 2$, these tasks can be solved under any number of crashes, because their SOS graph is necessarily connected.

► **Definition 5** (Validity-less k -set agreement). *Given the universe of values \mathbb{V} containing at least $k + 1$ values, an SOS task T_O with SOS O is validity-less k -set agreement if and only if $O = \{o \subseteq \mathbb{V} \mid 0 < |o| \leq k\}$.*

For instance, given the universe of values $\mathbb{V} = \{1, 2, 3\}$, the SOS of validity-less 2-set agreement is $O = \{\{1\}, \{2\}, \{3\}, \{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, \{2, 3\}\}$. The SOS graph associated with O is connected, so validity-less 2-set agreement can be solved with any number of crashes. More generally,

► **Corollary 6** (Solvability of validity-less k -set agreement with $k \geq 2$). *If $k \geq 2$, then validity-less k -set agreement is solvable under any number of crashes t .*

Proof. Since $k \geq 2$, the universe \mathbb{V} has at least 3 values, and O contains every nonempty subset of \mathbb{V} of size at most k . Hence, every output set $o \in O$ is connected to (or is itself) a singleton $\{v\} \in O$ (property 1), and any two singletons $\{v\}, \{v'\} \in O$ are connected via the path $\{v\} \subset \{v, v'\} \subset \{v'\}$, since $\{v, v'\} \in O$ whenever $k \geq 2$ (property 2). Together, these imply that $SOSGraph(O)$ is connected, so the result follows from Algorithm 1 via Theorem 4. ◀

4 The d -Disagreement Problem

In the previous section, we saw that all connected SOS tasks can be implemented using Algorithm 1. However, this algorithm makes a strong system assumption, namely, that there is at least one correct process for every possible output value. This raises a new question: Can we identify some subclasses of connected SOS tasks with better implementability conditions? We now turn to this question for a natural family of connected SOS tasks, called d -disagreement, and that requires every execution to produce exactly $d \geq 1$ distinct output values. Formally, a d -disagreement SOS task T_O has SOS $O = \{\{v_1, \dots, v_d\}\}$. As d -disagreement seeks to bound the *minimum* number of different decision values, it belongs to the *symmetry breaking* family of distributed problems (in contrast to *agreement* problems, which seek to bound the *maximum* number of different decision values).

In the following, we first present in Section 4.1 an impossibility proof on the implementability of d -disagreement, namely, that it can be implemented under asynchrony only if $n \geq \sum_{i=1}^d \lceil \frac{t+1}{i} \rceil$. Notice that this bound approximates (up to the iterated rounding) to the d -th harmonic number times $t + 1$. We then provide in Section 4.2 an asynchronous implementation of d -disagreement that assumes $n \geq d \lceil \frac{t+1}{2} \rceil + \lfloor \frac{t+1}{2} \rfloor$.

4.1 Impossibility of d -disagreement

► **Theorem 7** (Necessity of d -disagreement). *Under asynchrony, condition $n \geq \sum_{i=1}^d \lceil \frac{t+1}{i} \rceil$ is necessary for implementing the sets of output sets $O = \{\{v_1, \dots, v_d\}\}$.*

Proof. For simplicity of presentation, in this proof, we assume the existence of a global clock that is inaccessible to the processes. By contradiction, let us assume that there exists an algorithm A that implements the set of output sets $\{\{v_1, \dots, v_d\}\}$ under asynchrony and $n < \sum_{i=1}^d \lceil \frac{t+1}{i} \rceil$. We present an execution E of A that violates this assumption.

The execution E of A (with t crashes) is illustrated in Figure 2, and corresponds to the concatenation of execution fragments described as follows. Let us consider the first fragment of E , denoted E^1 , which starts at time 0. Initially, we let the processes run A freely until the first process p_1^1 is about to output some value v_1^1 at a time τ_1^1 . Process p_1^1 is frozen at time τ_1^1 , so no other process can observe v_1^1 (for now). Then, we let the non-frozen processes run A freely until a second process p_1^2 is about to output some value v_1^2 at a time τ_1^2 , which is also frozen at τ_1^2 so no other process can observe v_1^2 . We repeat this process until process p_1^{t+1} is about to output value v_1^{t+1} and is frozen at time τ_1^{t+1} . This is the time execution fragment E^1 ends. (Remark that, if there are enough processes, such a process p_1^{t+1} must exist, since otherwise at most t processes output values in the execution; then, crashing them instead of freezing them would create an execution that can not produce the output set $\{v_1, \dots, v_d\}$.) Let w_1 be the most frequent value in v_1^1, \dots, v_1^{t+1} , and P_1 be the subset of processes that output w_1 in E^1 . Observe that $|P_1| \geq \lceil \frac{t+1}{d} \rceil$. Let us denote $c_1 = |P_1|$.

Let us now consider the second fragment, E^2 , which starts at time τ_1^{t+1} . Initially, in this fragment, all processes in P_1 are thawed, so they can go ahead and output w_1 . Then, we let the non-frozen processes run freely A as long as they only output value w_1 . We stop when a process p_2^1 is about to output some value $v_2^1 \neq w_1$ at a time τ_2^1 . Process p_2^1 is then frozen at time τ_2^1 , so no other process can observe v_2^1 . We repeat this c_1 times until there are (again) $t+1$ frozen processes. At this time $\tau_2^{c_1}$ when execution fragment E^2 ends. (By the same argument as before, this must always happen if there are enough processes.) Let w_2 be the most frequent value to be output by the frozen processes and P_2 be the subset of frozen processes that output w_2 . Since w_1 is not output by any frozen process, we have that $c_2 = |P_2| \geq \lceil \frac{t+1}{d-1} \rceil$.

The third fragment E^3 is constructed similarly. It starts at time $\tau_2^{c_1}$ by thawing all processes in P_2 . Then, we let non-frozen processes run A , while freezing the first c_2 processes that are about to output values not in $\{w_1, w_2\}$. When this happens (at time $\tau_3^{c_2}$), fragment E^3 ends with $t+1$ frozen processes. Let w_3 be the most frequent value to be output by the frozen processes and P_3 be the subset of frozen processes that output w_3 . Since $w_3 \notin \{w_1, w_2\}$, we have that $c_3 = |P_3| \geq \lceil \frac{t+1}{d-2} \rceil$.

Each execution fragment E^i , for $i = 4, \dots, d-1$, is constructed inductively in a similar way. It starts at time $\tau_{i-1}^{c_{i-2}}$ by thawing all processes in P_{i-1} , so they can output w_{i-1} . Then, we let non-frozen processes run A , while freezing the first c_{i-1} processes that are about to output values not in $\{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{i-1}\}$. When this happens (at time $\tau_i^{c_{i-1}}$) fragment E^i ends with $t+1$ frozen processes. Let w_i be the most frequent value to be output by the frozen processes and P_i be the subset of frozen processes that output w_i . Since $w_i \notin \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{i-1}\}$, we have that $c_i = |P_i| \geq \lceil \frac{t+1}{d-i+1} \rceil$.

■ **Figure 2** Execution E , where all processes in the set P_d crash.

■ **Algorithm 2** Asynchronous d -disagreement algorithm for every SOS task with $O = \{v_1, \dots, v_d\}$, assuming $n \geq d \lceil \frac{t+1}{2} \rceil + \lfloor \frac{t+1}{2} \rfloor$.

```

1 initialization: create partition  $P_1, \dots, P_d, P_\gamma$  of  $P$  s.t.
    $|P_\gamma| = n - d \lceil \frac{t+1}{2} \rceil, \forall i \in [1..d] : |P_i| = \lceil \frac{t+1}{2} \rceil$ .
2 code of every process  $p_i \in P_i, i \in [1..d]$  is
3    $\text{output } v_i;$ 
4    $\text{communicate OUTPUT}(v_i)$ .
5 code of every process  $p_\gamma \in P_\gamma$  is
6    $\text{wait until } p_\gamma \text{ observed } d-1 \text{ distinct OUTPUT}(\star);$ 
7    $V_{\text{obs}} \leftarrow \{v \mid p_i \text{ observed OUTPUT}(v)\};$ 
8    $\text{output } v \in \{v_1, \dots, v_d\} \setminus V_{\text{obs}}.$ 

```

The final execution fragment E^d starts at time $\tau_{d-1}^{c_{d-2}}$ by thawing all processes in P_{d-1} , so they can output w_{d-1} . Observe that all the remaining frozen processes are about to output the only value $w_d \in \{v_1, \dots, v_d\}$ that is not in $\{w_1, \dots, w_{d-1}\}$. Then, we let non-frozen processes run A , while freezing the first $c_{d-1} - 1$ processes that are about to output value w_d . When this happens (at time $\tau_d^{c_{d-1}}$) fragment E^d ends with a set P_d of $c_d = t$ frozen processes. At that time, we crash the t processes of P_d , so they never output value w_d . This is the time execution E ends, since all processes either have output a value or crashed, given that $\sum_{i=1}^d |P_i| = \sum_{i=1}^d \lceil \frac{t+1}{2} \rceil - 1 \geq n$. By construction, the set of values $\{v_1, \dots, v_d\}$ has not been produced in execution E . Hence, we have a contradiction. ◀

4.2 Implementation of d -disagreement

In this section, we present Algorithm 2, an asynchronous implementation of the d -disagreement SOS task T_O , where $O = \{v_1, \dots, v_d\}$, assuming $n \geq d \lceil \frac{t+1}{2} \rceil + \lfloor \frac{t+1}{2} \rfloor$. At the initialization of the algorithm, the set of all processes P is partitioned into $d+1$ subsets, $P_1, \dots, P_d, P_\gamma$, such that $|P_\gamma| = n - d \lceil \frac{t+1}{2} \rceil$, and for every $i \in [1..d]$, $|P_i| = \lceil \frac{t+1}{2} \rceil$ (line 1).³ We can easily see that the assumption $n \geq d \lceil \frac{t+1}{2} \rceil + \lfloor \frac{t+1}{2} \rfloor$ is sufficient to instantiate all sets of processes $P_1, \dots, P_d, P_\gamma$. Remark that $|P_\gamma| = n - d \lceil \frac{t+1}{2} \rceil \geq \lfloor \frac{t+1}{2} \rfloor$. Therefore, this construction guarantees that, in any pair of subsets P_i, P_j of the partition, there is always at least one correct process.⁴

For every subset $P_i, i \in [1..d]$, a process $p_i \in P_i$ outputs v_i (line 3) and then communicates $\text{OUTPUT}(v_i)$ (line 4). Moreover, every process $p_\gamma \in P_\gamma$ waits until it observes $d-1$ distinct $\text{OUTPUT}(\star)$ (line 6), and gathers the observed values in the set V_{obs} (line 7). Finally, p_γ outputs the only value that is not present in V_{obs} (line 8).

► **Theorem 8** (Correctness of Algorithm 2). *Algorithm 2 implements all d -disagreement SOS tasks T_O with SOS $O = \{v_1, \dots, v_d\}$ under asynchrony and up to t crash failures, assuming $n \geq d \lceil \frac{t+1}{2} \rceil + \lfloor \frac{t+1}{2} \rfloor$.*

Proof. We prove the safety and completeness of Algorithm 2 as follows.

Safety Let us consider an arbitrary execution E , and let Π be the set of all subsets of processes of the partition $P_1, \dots, P_d, P_\gamma$ such that each $P \in \Pi$ contains at least one correct process $p \in P$ in execution E . By construction of line 1, it is impossible to crash all the

³ Note that any construction of $P_1, \dots, P_d, P_\gamma$ such that the union of two subsets is strictly greater than t also works.

⁴ Recall that, $\forall k \in \mathbb{N} : k = \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor + \lceil \frac{k}{2} \rceil$.

processes of two subsets of $P_1, \dots, P_d, P_?$, so we have $d \leq |\Pi| \leq d + 1$. We now consider the following two cases.

1. Case (i): $P_? \notin \Pi$. In this case, we necessarily have $\Pi = \{P_1, \dots, P_d\}$, thus there exists at least one correct process p_i in every subset $P_i, i \in [1..d]$ that outputs v_i at line 3. Therefore, such an execution necessarily produces the output set $\{v_1, \dots, v_d\}$.
2. Case (ii): $P_? \in \Pi$. In this case, there can be at most one subset of P_1, \dots, P_d that does not belong to Π . Let $\Pi' = \Pi \setminus \{P_?\}$ be the set of subsets of processes in P_1, \dots, P_d that contain correct processes in execution E . We necessarily have $|\Pi'| \geq d - 1$. For every subset $P_i \in \Pi'$, there is at least one correct process $p_i \in P_i$ that outputs v_i at line 3 and then communicates $\text{OUTPUT}(v_i)$ at line 4. By C-Local-Termination and C-Global-Termination, the correct processes $p_? \in P_?$ eventually observe $d - 1$ distinct $\text{OUTPUT}(v)$ in line 6 (by case assumption, there is at least one correct process in $P_?$). By construction, the set V_{obs} of every correct process $p_? \in P_?$ therefore contains $d - 1$ different values at line 7 (though the set V_{obs} may differ between correct processes of $P_?$). For every correct process $p_? \in P_?$, $\{v_1, \dots, v_d\} \setminus V_{\text{obs}}$ contains exactly one value $v \in \{v_1, \dots, v_d\}$. Finally, every correct process $p_? \in P_?$ outputs the only value $v \in \{v_1, \dots, v_d\} \setminus V_{\text{obs}}$ (line 8) that has not been observed by $p_?$. Hence, the execution produces the output set $\{v_1, \dots, v_d\}$.

Completeness Since there is only one output set in O , and safety shows that any execution produces this unique output set, then completeness follows immediately. ◀

5 Related Work

Combinatorial topology for distributed computing As discussed earlier, combinatorial topology has found surprising applications in the study of distributed tasks, as exposed in the monograph by Herlihy, Kozlov, and Rajsbaum [12]. This approach finds its roots in STOC 1993, where three concurrent papers leveraged combinatorial or topological results [5, 19, 14] (journal versions: [6, 15, 20]), such as Sperner’s lemma or Brouwer’s fixed point theorem, to prove the impossibility of k -set agreement under asynchrony and k crashes [8]. Specifically, the last two papers [19, 14] (which won the 2004 Gödel prize) proved this impossibility in the wait-free case, while the first one [5] (which won the 2017 Dijkstra prize) introduces the *BG simulation* technique, extending the impossibility to the general case. Broadly speaking, BG simulation shows that adding more correct processes to a wait-free system does not increase its computability power, for a specific class of tasks called convergence tasks [6] (also called *colorless* tasks), which correspond to the tasks whose input and output domains are “closed under inclusion”.

Decidability of distributed tasks We focus on the asynchronous crash-prone model, as most of the literature on distributed decidability studied this particular model (indeed, many of the hardest problems, such as consensus, become solvable with any number of Byzantine/crash faults under synchrony [17]). Moran and Wolfstahl generalized the famous impossibility of consensus [9] by proving that all tasks that have a connected *input graph* and disconnected *output graph* do not tolerate crashes [18] (informally, the input (resp. output) graph is constructed by linking the input (resp. output) vectors that differ by only one value). This result was later completed by Biran, Moran, and Zaks, who demonstrated the decidability of tasks in the 1-resilient message-passing model (later shown to be equivalent to 1-resilient shared memory [3]), notably by introducing a general algorithm solving all 1-resilient tasks in their classification [4]. In the same vein, Taubenfeld, Katz, and Moran showed the decidability of tasks in the presence of initial failures [22]. The first *undecidability* result of

distributed computing is due to Gafni and Koutsoupias, who, by drawing connections with the contractability problem in topology, showed that some 3-process tasks are undecidable in the shared-memory wait-free model (i.e., with 2 crashes), that is, it is impossible to say if these tasks are solvable or not [10]. This undecidability result has been extended to other communication models and arbitrary levels of resilience by Herlihy and Rajsbaum [13]. The known decidability results of distributed tasks in the asynchronous crash-prone model are summarized in Table 2.

The SOS approach The present work is closest to that of Albouy *et al.* [2], who introduced the Set of Output Sets approach in the binary case (i.e., the output values are 0 or 1). However, they did not formally define the concept of SOS tasks. In contrast, our formalization of *SOS tasks* can capture both binary and multivalued output sets, and it allows us to transfer the tightness results of [2] to a precise class of tasks, noted “Binary SOS tasks” (*) in Table 2.

6 Conclusions

In this paper, we introduce and study SOS tasks, a novel class of distributed tasks defined by the set of distinct output sets they can produce across their executions. By departing from the classical triplet-based formalization of tasks and from the constraints of simplicial complexes, we have developed a framework that accommodates multiple valid implementations and output domains that are not closed under inclusion.

Our main result establishes that the entire class of SOS tasks is decidable under asynchrony and any number of crashes. The decision rule is remarkably simple: an SOS task is always solvable when no process may crash, and it is solvable under any positive number of crashes if and only if its SOS graph (whose vertices are the output sets and whose edges connect pairs related by inclusion) is connected. This clean dichotomy partitions SOS tasks into those that tolerate arbitrarily many crashes and those that tolerate none at all, with no intermediate regime.

Our decidability result has yielded several noteworthy consequences. First, it reveals a sharp discontinuity in the landscape of k -set agreement: without validity, k -set agreement is solvable under any number of crashes for $k \geq 2$, yet becomes impossible under even a single crash when $k = 1$ (consensus). This highlights that the classical impossibility of k -set agreement for $k \geq 2$ fundamentally depends on the validity requirement, a dependency that does not exist for consensus, whose impossibility holds even in its validity-less form. Second, our study of d -disagreement, a symmetry-breaking task requiring the system to always produce exactly d distinct output values, has uncovered a surprising connection to the harmonic series: the number of processes necessary to solve d -disagreement under t crashes is approximately $n \geq H_d(t + 1)$, where H_d is the d -th harmonic number.

Several directions for future work emerge naturally from this study. First, closing the gap between the lower bound of $\sum_{i=1}^d \lceil \frac{t+1}{i} \rceil$ and the upper bound of $d \lceil \frac{t+1}{2} \rceil + \lfloor \frac{t+1}{2} \rfloor$ for d -disagreement remains an open problem, and an optimal algorithm would be of both theoretical and practical interest, particularly for fault-tolerant load balancing applications. Second,

Family	Condition on crashes	Decidable	Reference
Arbitrary tasks	$t \geq 2$	No	[10, 13]
	$t = 1$	Yes	[4, 3, 18]
	initial crashes	Yes	[22]
Binary SOS tasks (*)	any $t \leq n$	Yes	[2]
SOS tasks	any $t \leq n$	Yes	This work

■ **Table 2** Decidability results on distributed tasks identified to date (under asynchrony and crashes).

the universal algorithm we have presented for connected SOS tasks (Algorithm 1) requires $n \geq (t + 1)|V|$ processes. It would be valuable to determine tight resilience bounds, that is, the exact relationship between n and t for which each connected SOS task becomes solvable. Third, and perhaps most ambitiously, our work suggests a broader program: extending the decidability analysis to richer classes of tasks, such as tasks defined by their set of output vectors (rather than output sets), or tasks that incorporate input-dependent specifications. By progressively mapping the boundary between decidable and undecidable families, we hope to contribute to an eventual comprehensive theory of distributed decidability, one that plays a role for distributed computing analogous to that of classical computability theory for sequential computing.

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Appendix

A Correctness of Algorithm 1

In this section, we prove Theorem 4, stating the correctness of Algorithm 1. We first show some preliminary results. In the following, we denote by *LeadersOutputSets* the set containing all output sets o from the $\text{OUTPUTSET}(o)$ communicated by the group of leader processes P_{leader} during an execution of Algorithm 3.

► **Lemma 9.** *LeadersOutputSets is nonempty.*

Proof. As $|P_{\text{leader}}| > t$ by construction, there is at least one non-faulty leader process $p_{\text{leader}} \in P_{\text{leader}}$. Recall that SOSWalk_O is necessarily of finite size. For some loop index $i \in [1..|\text{SOSWalk}_O|]$, p_{leader} eventually enters the condition at line 5 for one of the following reasons:

- the communication was delayed due to asynchrony, and p_{leader} did not observe all $\text{MOVE}(i+1)$ by the end of the wait at line 6;
- some leader process $p'_{\text{leader}} \in P_{\text{leader}}$ did not communicate $\text{MOVE}(i+1)$, either because p'_{leader} crashed, or because o_i was the last element of SOSWalk_O at line 5.

Hence, process p_{leader} eventually communicates some $\text{OUTPUTSET}(o_i)$ at line 8, and therefore *LeadersOutputSets* is nonempty. ◀

► **Lemma 10.** *For every output set $o_i \in \text{SOSWalk}_O$, there exists an execution of Algorithm 1 for which $\text{LeadersOutputSets} = \{o_i\}$.*

Proof. As SOSWalk_O is a sequence, every element $o_i \in \text{SOSWalk}_O$ has a finite index $i \in \mathbb{N}^*$. There must exist a crash-free execution where, for every loop index $j \in [1..i-1]$, every leader process communicates $\text{MOVE}(j+1)$ at line 5, observes all $|P_{\text{leader}}|$ $\text{MOVE}(o_j+1)$ by the end of the wait at line 6, and therefore skips the condition at line 7. (If $i=1$, then the loop is executed only once.) At the end of this procedure, loop index i is reached. There must exist a crash-free execution that reaches this stage, and all leader processes do not observe all $|P_{\text{leader}}|$ $\text{MOVE}(i+1)$ by the end of the wait at line 6 due to asynchrony (since any timing of observations consistent with the communication properties is admissible, see Section 2.1). Thus, all leader processes enter the condition at line 7, communicate $\text{OUTPUTSET}(o_i)$ at line 8, and exit the loop at line 9. Hence, $\text{LeadersOutputSets} = \{o_i\}$. ◀

► **Observation 11.** *By construction (lines 4 and 8), all elements of LeadersOutputSets are in SOSWalk_O .*

► **Lemma 12.** *LeadersOutputSets is either of the form $\{o_i\}$ or of the form $\{o_i, o_{i+1}\}$, where o_i, o_{i+1} are two subsequent elements in SOSWalk_O .*

Proof. Lemma 9 shows that *LeadersOutputSets* cannot be empty. Lemma 10 implies the existence of some executions where *LeadersOutputSets* is a singleton $\{o_i\}$ where $o_i \in \text{SOSWalk}_O$.

Let us consider an execution where *LeadersOutputSets* is at least of size 2. By Observation 11, *LeadersOutputSets* contains elements of SOSWalk_O , and therefore we can consider any two distinct output sets $o_i, o_j \in \text{LeadersOutputSets}$, where i and j are the indices of o_i, o_j in SOSWalk_O such that $i < j$. By definition of *LeadersOutputSets*, there is one leader process $p_{\text{leader}} \in P_{\text{leader}}$ that communicated some $\text{OUTPUTSET}(o_i)$ at line 8, during the loop iteration i , and then exited the loop at line 9. Therefore, p_{leader} could not have communicated $\text{MOVE}(i+2)$ during the loop iteration $i+1$, and every leader process that reaches the loop iteration $i+1$ thus enters the condition at line 7, communicates $\text{OUTPUTSET}(o_{i+1})$ at line 8

and exits the loop at line 9. It follows that $j = i + 1$, and thus that $LeadersOutputSets$ is of the form $\{o_i, o_{i+1}\}$. ◀

► **Lemma 13.** *In an execution with a given set $LeadersOutputSets$, the set of output values produced by the execution is $o = \bigcup LeadersOutputSets$.*

Proof. Let us consider an execution with set $LeadersOutputSets$, let $o = \bigcup LeadersOutputSets$ be the set of all values appearing in $LeadersOutputSets$, and let $V = \bigcup O$ be the set of all values appearing in O .

By definition, $LeadersOutputSets$ is the set of all output sets o' that have been communicated by leader processes in some $OUTPUTSET(o')$ at line 8. By C-Local-Termination and C-Global-Termination, all correct processes eventually observe all of these $OUTPUTSET(o')$. Since the union of all $o' \in LeadersOutputSets$ is o , and by Observation 11, we deduce that $o \subseteq V$. As $|P_v| > t$ for every $v \in V$, there is at least one correct process $p_v \in P_v$ that outputs v at line 10 upon observing the first $OUTPUTSET(o')$ such that $v \in o'$. Therefore, as a whole, the execution produces output set o . ◀

For completeness, we restate Theorem 4.

THEOREM 3.3 (CORRECTNESS OF ALGORITHM 1). *Algorithm 1 implements any given connected SOS task T_O with SOS O under asynchrony and up to t crash failures, assuming $n \geq (t + 1) \cdot |V_O|$, where $V = \bigcup O$ is the set of all possible output value in O .*

Proof. We prove the safety and completeness of Algorithm 1 as follows.

Safety Let us consider an arbitrary execution of Algorithm 1 with set $LeadersOutputSets$. By Lemma 12, there are only two cases: (i) $LeadersOutputSets = \{o_i\}$, or (ii) $LeadersOutputSets = \{o_i, o_{i+1}\}$, where o_i, o_{i+1} are two subsequent elements in $SOSWalk_O$. Lemma 13 shows that the output set produced by the execution is $o = \bigcup LeadersOutputSets$. For case (i), the output set of the execution is $o = \bigcup \{o_i\} = o_i$, which is a valid output set of O . For case (ii), as o_i, o_{i+1} are subsequent elements in $SOSWalk_O$, then they are linked by an edge in the SOS graph $SOSGraph(O)$. By Definition 2, one of these two sets must include the other. Without loss of generality, let us assume that $o_i \subset o_{i+1}$. Thus, the output set of the execution is $o = \bigcup \{o_i, o_{i+1}\} = o_{i+1}$, which is also a valid output set of O . Therefore, any execution of Algorithm 1 produces a valid output set.

Completeness By Lemma 10, for every output set $o \in O$, there exists an execution in which $LeadersOutputSets = \{o_i\}$. By Lemma 13, the output set produced by this execution is o_i . ◀

B The Case of Non-Resilient SOS tasks

We provide in this section the remaining results of our decidability study of SOS tasks, namely, that all disconnected SOS tasks cannot be solved under asynchrony and crashes (Appendix B.1), that all SOS tasks can be solved asynchronously without crashes (Appendix B.2), and that $n \geq \max\{|o| : o \in O\}$ and $t = 0$ are tight conditions to implement disconnected SOS tasks asynchronously (Appendix B.3).

B.1 Necessity: The unsolvability of disconnected SOS tasks under crashes

In this section, we present Theorem 24, which generalizes the famous impossibility of asynchronous resilient consensus (FLP theorem [9]) to a broader family of tasks with non-

connected SOS graphs. Results similar to Theorem 24 have already been shown [18, 4], however, they rely on model-specific arguments (esp. message passing) and on a reduction from the consensus problem. Therefore, the FLP theorem is not a consequence of these results, but a cause. In contrast, our proof of Theorem 24 is agnostic of the underlying communication medium, and the impossibility is proved from scratch, which allows us to state the FLP theorem as a corollary of our theorem (Corollary 26).

Our proof generalizes the axiomatic approach of [1]: asynchrony, crash resilience, and termination are defined as axioms, and the impossibility of implementation is expressed as a contradiction within this system of axioms. We also generalize the classical notion of *valence*, introduced in [9]. However, unlike [1, 9], we extend the impossibility proof to any disconnected SOS task.

B.1.1 Preliminaries

We now introduce the necessary notions for our proof.

Events An *event* e_p^i is an action involving process p at index i (i.e., e_p^i is the i^{th} event of p).

The only purpose of event indices is to differentiate events on the same process that could swap orders due to asynchrony. For instance, in asynchronous message passing, two messages could be sent by two different senders p', p'' to the same recipient p , and due to asynchrony, there could be one execution where p first receives p' and then p'' , and another execution where p first receives p'' and then p' . However, thanks to indices, the reception by p of the message from p' in these two executions is considered as two different events, since the indices of these events are different. Apart from this technical detail, the event indices are not used in the rest of the proof.

Some special events, the input and output events, respectively, correspond to the input/output of a value v by a process p in the context of the task. These events are respectively noted in_p^v and out_p^v . If the process p and/or index i of some event are not relevant, we can omit writing them.

States A *state* σ is a set of events. An algorithm A is described by its set of states Σ and set of *output states* $\Omega \subseteq \Sigma$, which are the final states where the algorithm can terminate. By definition, all maximal states of Σ are output states, i.e., $\{\sigma \in \Sigma \mid \nexists \sigma' \in \Sigma, \sigma \subsetneq \sigma'\} \subseteq \Omega$, but let us remark that there can also be output states that are subsets of the maximal states. Conversely, the *input states* are the states from which the algorithm begins and that have no previous state. They are given by:

$$InStates(\Sigma) = \{\sigma \in \Sigma \mid \nexists \sigma' \in \Sigma : \sigma' \subsetneq \sigma\}.$$

► **Definition 14** (Input/output states of an implementation of task instance). *If an algorithm with a set of states Σ and a set of output states Ω implements the task instance τ of some task T , then there must be input/output states corresponding to every pair of input/output vectors in τ :*

$$\begin{aligned} \forall (V_{in}, V_{out}) \in \tau, \exists \sigma_{in} \in InStates(\Sigma), \exists \sigma_{out} \in \Omega : \sigma_{in} \subseteq \sigma_{out} \\ \wedge \{in_{p_j}^v \mid v \text{ is the } j^{\text{th}} \text{ value in } V_{in}, v \neq \perp\} = \sigma_{in} \\ \wedge \{out_{p_j}^v \mid v \text{ is the } j^{\text{th}} \text{ value in } V_{out}, v \neq \perp\} \subseteq \sigma_{out}. \end{aligned}$$

► **Definition 15** (SOS valence). *Given a set of states Σ , a set of output states Ω , and a state*

$\sigma \in \Sigma$, the SOS valence of σ is a set of sets of output values given by the function:

$$\text{Val}(\sigma, \Sigma, \Omega) = \begin{cases} \{\{v \mid \text{out}_p^v \in \sigma\}\} & \text{if } \sigma \in \Omega, \\ \bigcup_{\sigma' \in \{\sigma' \in \Sigma \mid \sigma \subsetneq \sigma'\}} \text{Val}(\sigma') & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Informally, the SOS valence of an output state is the singleton containing the output set it produces, and the SOS valence of any other state is the union of the SOS valence of all its extensions. (Let us note that this definition of valence differs from that of [1, 9], since here SOS valence is the set of reachable *sets* of output values, and not the set of reachable output values, as executions producing multiple output values are allowed in our context.)

B.1.2 Axioms

Here, we define asynchrony, resilience, and termination as axioms that some algorithm must satisfy. In these definitions, and in the rest of the proof, we use the symbol \uplus to denote the union of two disjoint sets.

► **Definition 16** (Asynchrony axiom). *Given a set of states Σ , asynchrony is defined as:*

$$\text{Asynchrony}(\Sigma) = \forall \sigma \in \Sigma : (\sigma \uplus \{e_p\}, \sigma \uplus \{e_{p'}\} \in \Sigma, p \neq p') \implies (\sigma \uplus \{e_p, e_{p'}\} \in \Sigma).$$

Asynchrony (sometimes referred to as the *diamond property*) requires that if two states differ only in their last respective events, which are from different processes, their union is also a state, as the pace of processes can change across two executions. We point out that our impossibility proof is agnostic of the communication medium object, as long as the medium satisfies asynchrony as defined above (which is the case for the **communicate/observe** abstraction used in this paper).⁵

► **Definition 17** (Termination axiom). *Given a set of states Σ , termination is defined as:*

$$\text{Termination}(\Sigma) = \forall \sigma \in \Sigma : |\sigma| < +\infty.$$

Termination ensures that an algorithm does not have any state with an infinite number of events, and thus that the output states are reached in a finite number of steps. One could argue that it is allowed for an algorithm to keep making steps indefinitely after reaching an output state, but without loss of generality, we omit this scenario by removing the states extending an output state.

► **Definition 18** (Resilience axiom). *Given a set of states Σ and set of output states $\Omega \subseteq \Sigma$, resilience is defined as:*

$$\text{Resilience}(\Sigma, \Omega) = \forall \sigma \in \Sigma \setminus \Omega, \exists \sigma \uplus \{e_p\}, \sigma \uplus \{e_{p'}\} \in \Sigma : p \neq p'.$$

Resilience imposes that at least two distinct processes can extend every state that is not an output state. If this is not the case, that is, if a state that is not an output state can only be extended by at most one process, then crashing this process would make the algorithm stop progressing, and thus never reach termination.

⁵ For a proof that some classical communication media (such as asynchronous message-passing and atomic memory) satisfy this definition of asynchrony, we refer the interested reader to [1].

B.1.3 Proof

Before proceeding to the impossibility theorem, we first establish some preliminary results. For notational simplicity, given a set of states Σ and a set of output states Ω , we say that a state $\sigma \in \Sigma$ is *disconnected* if its SOS valence has an associated SOS graph $SOSGraph(Val(\sigma, \Sigma, \Omega))$ that is disconnected, otherwise we say that state σ is *connected*.

► **Observation 19.** *Given a set of states Σ and a set of output states $\Omega \subseteq \Sigma$, by Definition 2, a disconnected σ cannot contain the empty set in its SOS valence $Val(\sigma, \Sigma, \Omega)$, because \emptyset is included in any other set, which would make σ connected.*

► **Lemma 20.** *Let O be an SOS whose SOS graph $SOSGraph(O)$ is disconnected, and let C_1, \dots, C_k ($k \geq 2$) be its connected components (expressed as sets of vertices). If $O' \subseteq O$ and $SOSGraph(O')$ is connected, then $O' \subseteq C_i$ for some $i \in [1..k]$.*

Proof. By definition of connected components, there is no edge in $SOSGraph(O)$ between any vertex in C_i and any vertex in C_j for $i \neq j$. Since edges in $SOSGraph(O')$ are a subset of those in $SOSGraph(O)$, if O' contained vertices from two distinct components C_i and C_j , then $SOSGraph(O')$ would itself be disconnected. Contradiction. ◀

► **Lemma 21.** *Given a set of states Σ and a set of output states $\Omega \subseteq \Sigma$, all states $\sigma \in \Sigma$ have a nonempty SOS valence: $Val(\sigma, \Sigma, \Omega) \neq \emptyset$.*

Proof. Let us consider some state $\sigma \in \Sigma$. By definition, all maximal states of Σ (i.e., states that cannot be extended) are output states: $\{\sigma' \in \Sigma \mid \nexists \sigma'' \in \Sigma, \sigma' \subsetneq \sigma''\} \subseteq \Omega$. By Definition 15, the SOS valence of an output state σ' (and in particular of a maximal state) is the singleton containing all output values of σ' , and it is therefore not empty. State σ is either an output state, or it is a subset of an output state: $\exists \sigma' \in \Omega, \sigma \subseteq \sigma'$. Again, by Definition 15, the SOS valence of σ must include the SOS valence of σ' : $Val(\sigma', \Sigma, \Omega) \subseteq Val(\sigma, \Sigma, \Omega)$. Therefore, the SOS valence of σ is not empty. ◀

Note that the previous lemma forbids the existence of an SOS valence of \emptyset , but it does not forbid the existence of an SOS valence of $\{\emptyset\}$ (i.e., the empty output set may be allowed).

► **Lemma 22.** *Given a set of states Σ and a set of output states $\Omega \subseteq \Sigma$, all disconnected states $\sigma \in \Sigma$ are not output states, i.e., $\sigma \notin \Omega$.*

Proof. Let us consider some disconnected state $\sigma \in \Sigma$ with SOS valence $O = Val(\sigma, \Sigma, \Omega)$. That is, $SOSGraph(O)$ is disconnected. By definition of $SOSGraph()$ (Definition 2), there must exist at least two output sets $o, o' \in O$ such that $o \cap o' = \emptyset$. Therefore, $\bigcap O = \emptyset$. As there is no common value across all the output sets $o \in O$, then there cannot be any output event out_p^v in σ , and the set of output values of σ is the empty set \emptyset . But by Observation 19, as σ is disconnected, then O cannot contain the empty output set \emptyset , and thus \emptyset is not a valid output set where the algorithm can terminate. Therefore, $\sigma \notin \Omega$. ◀

► **Lemma 23.** *An algorithm A (with set of states Σ and set of output states $\Omega \subseteq \Sigma$) that solves a disconnected SOS task T_O must have a disconnected state: $\exists \sigma \in \Sigma : SOSGraph(Val(\sigma, \Sigma, \Omega))$ is a disconnected graph.*

Proof. By Definition 14, Σ must contain input/output states corresponding to every pair of input/output vectors in τ . By the fact that SOS tasks are validity-free (Definition 1), every input vector V_{in} of τ can yield all output vector V_{out} of τ . This implies that every input state can reach every output set $o \in O$, or more formally: $\forall \sigma_{in} \in InStates(\Sigma), \forall o \in$

$O, \exists \sigma_{out} \in \Omega, \sigma_{in} \subseteq \sigma_{out} : \{v \mid in_p^v \in \sigma_{out}\} = o$. By the definition of SOS valence (Definition 15), all input state therefore have the entire SOS O as their SOS valence, i.e., $\forall \sigma_{in} \in InStates : Val(\sigma_{in}, \Sigma, \Omega) = O$. By the fact that T_O is a disconnected SOS task, $SOSGraph(O)$ is a disconnected graph, and therefore any input state $\sigma_{in} \in InStates$ is disconnected. \blacktriangleleft

► **Theorem 24** (Non-resilience of disconnected SOS tasks). *A disconnected SOS task T_O can be implemented asynchronously only if $t = 0$.*

Proof. By way of contradiction, let us assume that there is an algorithm A that implements any instance $\tau \in T_O$ under asynchrony and $t > 0$, and where T_O is a disconnected SOS task with SOS O . Let us consider the set of states Σ and the set of output states $\Omega \subseteq \Sigma$ of A . As communication is asynchronous, $Asynchrony(\Sigma)$ is verified. Moreover, as $t > 0$, there can be at least one crash in the system, and $Resilience(\Sigma, \Omega)$ is verified. Finally, a task execution must terminate by definition, so $Termination(\Sigma)$ is verified.

By Lemma 23, disconnected states must exist. Let us consider any disconnected state $\sigma_m \in \Sigma$. We now inductively show that there exists what we call a *critical* state σ_c , i.e., a disconnected state that only has connected extensions:

$$\begin{aligned} \exists \sigma_c \in \Sigma : (&SOSGraph(Val(\sigma_c, \Sigma, \Omega)) \text{ is a disconnected graph}) \\ \wedge (\forall \sigma' \in \Sigma, \sigma_c \subsetneq \sigma' : &SOSGraph(Val(\sigma', \Sigma, \Omega)) \text{ is a connected graph}). \end{aligned}$$

As σ_m has a disconnected SOS valence, Lemma 22 implies that is not an output state, i.e., $\sigma_m \notin \Omega$. By $Resilience(\Sigma, \Omega)$, σ_m must have some extensions by one event. If all extensions have an connected SOS valence, then σ_m satisfies the property of a critical state and we set $\sigma_c = \sigma_m$. Otherwise, σ_m has some extension by one event $\sigma_m \uplus \{e\} \in \Sigma$ that has a disconnected SOS valence. Then, we make σ_m this new extension $\sigma_m \uplus \{e\}$ and repeat this procedure. Observe that this process must eventually end by finding a critical state, since otherwise, it means that an infinite state exists, which contradicts $Termination(\Sigma)$.

Let $O_c = Val(\sigma_c, \Sigma, \Omega)$. Since σ_c is disconnected, $SOSGraph(O_c)$ has at least two connected components (expressed as sets of vertices); fix two of them, C_1 and C_2 . We will now show that there exist two immediate 1-event extensions $\sigma_1 = \sigma_c \uplus \{e_p\}$ and $\sigma_2 = \sigma_c \uplus \{e_{p'}\}$ in Σ such that $Val(\sigma_1, \Sigma, \Omega) \subseteq C_1$ and $Val(\sigma_2, \Sigma, \Omega) \subseteq C_2$ (and in particular $Val(\sigma_1, \Sigma, \Omega) \cap Val(\sigma_2, \Sigma, \Omega) = \emptyset$).

By Definition 15, $O_c = \bigcup_{\sigma' \in \Sigma, \sigma_c \subsetneq \sigma'} Val(\sigma', \Sigma, \Omega)$. In particular, $O_c = \bigcup_{\sigma_c \uplus \{e\} \in \Sigma} Val(\sigma_c \uplus \{e\}, \Sigma, \Omega)$, since every extension of σ_c passes through some immediate 1-event extension. As O_c intersects both C_1 and C_2 , there exist immediate extensions σ_1, σ_2 with $Val(\sigma_1, \Sigma, \Omega) \cap C_1 \neq \emptyset$ and $Val(\sigma_2, \Sigma, \Omega) \cap C_2 \neq \emptyset$. By criticality of σ_c , both $Val(\sigma_1, \Sigma, \Omega)$ and $Val(\sigma_2, \Sigma, \Omega)$ have connected SOS graphs. Since $Val(\sigma_1, \Sigma, \Omega), Val(\sigma_2, \Sigma, \Omega) \subseteq O_c$, Lemma 20 implies that each is included in a single connected component of $SOSGraph(O_c)$. Hence $Val(\sigma_1, \Sigma, \Omega) \subseteq C_1$ and $Val(\sigma_2, \Sigma, \Omega) \subseteq C_2$, so $Val(\sigma_1, \Sigma, \Omega) \cap Val(\sigma_2, \Sigma, \Omega) = \emptyset$. We now derive a contradiction by considering two cases.

- Case 1: $p \neq p'$. Given that the processes of the two events are distinct, from $Asynchrony(\Sigma)$, we have $\sigma'' = \sigma_c \uplus \{e_p, e_{p'}\} \in \Sigma$. Since σ'' extends both σ_1 and σ_2 , Definition 15 gives $Val(\sigma'', \Sigma, \Omega) \subseteq Val(\sigma_1, \Sigma, \Omega) \cap Val(\sigma_2, \Sigma, \Omega) = \emptyset$. Thus $Val(\sigma'', \Sigma, \Omega) = \emptyset$, which contradicts Lemma 21.
- Case 2: $p = p'$. By $Resilience(\Sigma, \Omega)$ (since $\sigma_c \notin \Omega$ by Lemma 22), there exists an immediate extension $\sigma_3 = \sigma_c \uplus \{e_{p''}\} \in \Sigma$ with $p'' \neq p$. By criticality of σ_c , $Val(\sigma_3, \Sigma, \Omega)$ has a connected SOS graph. Since $Val(\sigma_3, \Sigma, \Omega) \subseteq O_c$, Lemma 20 implies $Val(\sigma_3, \Sigma, \Omega) \subseteq C_j$ for some j . Without loss of generality, suppose $Val(\sigma_3, \Sigma, \Omega) \cap C_1 = \emptyset$ (if $Val(\sigma_3, \Sigma, \Omega) \subseteq C_1$,

use C_2 and σ_2 instead in the following). Then $Val(\sigma_3, \Sigma, \Omega) \cap Val(\sigma_1, \Sigma, \Omega) = \emptyset$, since $Val(\sigma_1, \Sigma, \Omega) \subseteq C_1$. As $p'' \neq p$, by *Asynchrony*(Σ), $\sigma_c \uplus \{e_p, e_{p''}\} \in \Sigma$. Since this state extends both σ_1 and σ_3 , Definition 15 gives $Val(\sigma_c \uplus \{e_p, e_{p''}\}, \Sigma, \Omega) \subseteq Val(\sigma_1, \Sigma, \Omega) \cap Val(\sigma_3, \Sigma, \Omega) = \emptyset$, contradicting Lemma 21. \blacktriangleleft

B.1.4 A special case: consensus

The impossibility of asynchronous resilient consensus follows directly from Theorem 24, as consensus has a disconnected SOS. More formally, validity-less consensus can be defined in our SOS approach as follows.

► **Definition 25** (Validity-less consensus). *Validity-less consensus is an SOS task T_O with SOS O such that:*

1. $\forall o \in O : |o| = 1$, that is, every execution of consensus produces only one output value;
2. $|O| \geq 2$, that is, consensus has at least two different executions that produce different output values.

The first item of Definition 25 imposes that the system always agrees on one single output value, while the second item precludes trivial implementations that always output the same value across all executions. We can see that validity-less k -set agreement (Definition 5, page 9) boils down to validity-less consensus (Definition 25) when $k = 1$.

► **Corollary 26** (Impossibility of asynchronous resilient consensus (FLP theorem [9])). *Consensus is impossible under asynchrony and one crash.*

Proof. By Definition 25, validity-less consensus T_O has an SOS O which contains at least two different singletons $\{v\}, \{v'\} \in O$. Neither of these two singletons can include the other, hence $SOSGraph(O)$ is a disconnected graph. Therefore, Theorem 24 applies, which entails that validity-less consensus cannot be solved asynchronously with $t > 0$.

It is easy to see that validity-less consensus (Definition 25) is an even weaker problem than validity-based consensus, which must also guarantee that every execution produces an output value taken from the input values. Therefore, the impossibility of validity-less consensus implies the impossibility of validity-based consensus. \blacktriangleleft

B.2 Sufficiency: A non-resilient algorithm for disconnected SOS tasks

In this section, we present Algorithm 3, a universal algorithm that implements any SOS task T_O under asynchrony assuming $n \geq \max\{|o| : o \in O\}$, $n \geq 1$, and $t = 0$ (no crash). The algorithm is instantiated by providing the SOS O as a parameter (line 1). At the initialization of the algorithm (line 2), a leader process $p_{leader} \in P$ is selected. We also let m be the size of the biggest output set in O , and create a partition of all processes P_1, \dots, P_m containing m nonempty subsets (we can create this partition as we assume $n \geq \max\{|o| : o \in O\} = m$). To guarantee the existence of a leader, we assume that $n \geq 1$. However, we show in Appendix B.2.2 that the case of $n = 0$ can be trivially addressed.

First, for every output sets $o \in O$, the leader process p_{leader} communicates $CHOICE(o)$ at line 4. Then, p_{leader} waits for observing the first $CHOICE(o')$ at line 5, and finally, p_{leader} communicates $OUTPUTSET(o')$ at line 6. Besides, every process $p_i \in P$ (including p_{leader}) first waits for the $OUTPUTSET(o)$ communicated by p_{leader} (line 8). Then, p_i computes its output value $v_i \in o$ based on its subset index i in the partition ($1 \leq i \leq m$): more precisely, p_i sorts all values in o and takes the $((i \bmod |o|) + 1)$ -th one in this sequence (line 9). Finally, p_i outputs v_i (line 10).

B.2.1 Correctness of Algorithm 3

The correctness of Algorithm 3 is given in Theorem 28. We begin with an intermediary lemma.

► **Lemma 27.** *If p_{leader} communicates $OUTPUTSET(o)$ at line 6, then the execution produces output set o .*

Proof. Let us assume that p_{leader} communicates $OUTPUTSET(o)$ at line 6. By C-Local-Termination, C-Global-Termination, and the fact that there are no crashes, all processes eventually observe $OUTPUTSET(o)$ and pass the wait statement at line 8. By C-Validity and the fact that only p_{leader} communicates information in the algorithm, $OUTPUTSET(o)$ is the only information observed by the processes. We can first observe that the execution cannot produce output values that are not in o , by line 7.

Since all subsets in the partition P_1, \dots, P_m are nonempty and no process crashes, all processes $p_1 \in P_1$ pick the smallest value $v_1 \in o$, all processes $p_2 \in P_2$ pick the second smallest value v_2 , etc., and finally, all processes $p_{|o|} \in P_{|o|}$ pick the biggest value $v_{|o|} \in o$ (recall that $|o| \leq m$). After that, all processes $p_i \in P_i, i \in [1..|o|]$ output v_i at line 7. Therefore, as a whole, all processes of $P_1, \dots, P_{|o|}$ output all values in o , and the execution produces the output set o . ◀

► **Theorem 28.** *Algorithm 3 implements any SOS task T_O with SOS O under asynchrony, assuming $n \geq \max\{|o| : o \in O\}$, $n \geq 1$, and $t = 0$.*

Proof. The safety and completeness of Algorithm 3 are proved in the following.

Safety Let o be an output set produced by an execution of Algorithm 3, we will now show that $o \in O$. Since there is no crash, p_{leader} has observed at line 5 some $CHOICE(o')$ that it has communicated before (by C-Validity) and therefore $o_j \in O$ (from line 4). After that, p_{leader} communicated $OUTPUTSET(o')$ at line 6. By Lemma 27, the execution produces output set o' , and $o = o'$. As $o' \in O$, then $o \in O$.

Completeness For every $o \in O$, there must exist an execution where the first information observed by the leader process p_{leader} is $CHOICE(o)$ due to asynchrony (since any timing of observations consistent with the communication properties is admissible, see Section 2.1). By Lemma 27, the execution must produce the output set o . ◀

■ **Algorithm 3** Asynchronous algorithm implementing all possible SOS O assuming $n \geq \max\{|o| : o \in O\}$, $n \geq 1$, and $t = 0$.

1	instantiation parameter: SOS O .
2	initialization: pick some leader process $p_{leader} \in P$, let $m = \max\{ o : o \in O\}$, create a partition P_1, \dots, P_m of P s.t. $\forall i \in [1..m], P_i \geq 1$.
3	code of process p_{leader} is
4	for all $o \in O$ do communicate $CHOICE(o)$;
5	wait p_{leader} observes first $CHOICE(o')$;
6	communicate $OUTPUTSET(o')$.
7	code of every process $p_i \in P_i, i \in [1..m]$ is
8	wait p_i observes $OUTPUTSET(o)$;
9	$v_i \leftarrow ((i \bmod o) + 1)$ -th largest value in o ;
10	output v_i .

B.2.2 The case of $n = 0$

If there is no process in the system ($n = 0$), then Algorithm 3 cannot work as it requires the existence of some leader p_{leader} . However, with no process, the only SOS that can be produced is $O = \{\emptyset\}$, and any execution of an algorithm with no process necessarily already produces the output set \emptyset . Therefore, such an algorithm is trivially safe and complete.

B.3 Tight conditions to implement disconnected SOS tasks

In this section, we combine the previous results to show that the two conditions $n \geq \max\{|o| : o \in O\}$ and $t = 0$ are necessary and sufficient to implement any *disconnected* SOS task T_O in asynchrony. In the following, we consider an arbitrary SOS task T_O with a disconnected SOS O , i.e., $SOSGraph(O)$ is a disconnected graph.

Necessity of $n \geq \max\{|o| : o \in O\}$ and $t = 0$ The necessity of $t = 0$ comes from Theorem 24. The necessity of $n \geq \max\{|o| : o \in O\}$ comes from the fact that, if this condition is not satisfied, then there are not enough processes in the system to output all the values of the largest output set $o \in O$, violating completeness.

Sufficiency of $n \geq \max\{|o| : o \in O\}$ and $t = 0$ If $SOSGraph(O)$ is a disconnected graph, then it necessarily contains several vertices, and SOS O cannot be $\{\emptyset\}$. It implies that $n \geq 1$. Finally, if we assume that conditions $n \geq \max\{|o| : o \in O\}$ and $t = 0$ are satisfied, then we have all the sufficient conditions to use Algorithm 3 and implement the disconnected SOS task T_O .